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GOVERNANCE AND PERCEPTIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE: A STUDY OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION¹

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Abstract

The governance model established in an organization is directly related to the type of transactions it carries out. These transactions are marked by transaction costs, inherent to behavioral assumptions (opportunistic behavior and limited rationality) and other transaction factors (asset specificity, frequency, and uncertainty). The relationship between partners should be beneficial when there is a perception of fairness, especially at the initial stage of the relationship, when those involved are not yet completely familiar with the other partners' working methodologies. In this sense, the perception of fairness in the relationship improves and the predisposition to business should increase. Therefore, this study aimed to review scientific works in the international literature and how they dimension the impact of perceptions of organizational justice and relations between agents and the governance of organizations. The pattern of publications worldwide highlights the participation of developed countries in North America and Europe in the subject study, such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Denmark, for example. This research identified the characteristics of the agents that guide the relationships linked to the main theme of this paper, such as commitment, trust, insecurity, cooperation, and positive and negative feelings, for example. According to the authors, organizational justice has a positive impact on the relational governance performance of rural cooperatives. Likewise, they state that improving the level of governance is directly linked to the positive participation of members in the institution's internal governance.

Keywords: Governance; Organizational Justice; Perception; Systematic Review.

Resumo

O modelo de governança estabelecido em uma organização está diretamente relacionado ao tipo de transações que ela realiza. Estas transações são marcadas por custos de transação, inerentes a pressupostos comportamentais (comportamento oportunista e racionalidade limitada) e outros fatores de transação (especificidade dos ativos, frequência e incerteza). A relação entre parceiros deve ser benéfica quando existe uma percepção de justiça, especialmente na fase inicial da relação, quando os envolvidos ainda não estão completamente familiarizados com as metodologias de trabalho dos outros parceiros. Nesse sentido, melhora a percepção de justiça no relacionamento e a predisposição para negócios deve aumentar. Portanto, este estudo teve como objetivo revisar trabalhos científicos presentes na literatura internacional e como eles dimensionam o impacto das percepções de justiça organizacional e das relações entre os agentes e a governança das organizações. O padrão de publicações em todo o mundo destaca a participação de países desenvolvidos da América do Norte e da Europa no tema de estudo, como Estados Unidos, Reino Unido e Dinamarca, por exemplo. Esta pesquisa identificou as características dos agentes que orientam as relações vinculadas ao tema central deste artigo, como comprometimento, confiança, insegurança, cooperação e sentimentos positivos e negativos, por exemplo. Segundo os autores, a justiça organizacional tem impacto positivo no desempenho da governança relacional das cooperativas rurais. Da mesma forma, afirmam que a melhoria do nível de governança está diretamente ligada à participação positiva dos membros na governança interna da instituição.

Palavras-chave: Governança; Justiça Organizacional; Percepção; Revisão Sistemática.

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INTRODUCTION

According to the New Institutional Economics (NIE), most transactions have costs. From this perspective, it is possible to assess the efficiency and effectiveness of different arrangements, allowing the observation of economic patterns that can cause or influence processes in institutions.

The way in which agents behave is assessed by the Transaction Cost Theory (TCT). This study points out that during transactions, agents' rationality is limited and that their actions are biased towards opportunism, which makes this relationship very fragile. Not all agents are opportunistic, but the possibility of just one of them following this behavior and putting contractual agreements at risk already justifies monitoring. Therefore, good communication is fundamental to preventing opportunism through contractual flexibility.

However, there needs to be a bilateral character in the governance of organizations due to the need to build and strengthen relationships with a good reputation and trust on both sides, especially in order to seek fairness among transactions. Some theories believe that the use of such arguments is necessary when there are signs of problems related to loyalty and trust that could jeopardize the continuity of transactions. Therefore, the factors of loyalty and trust are fundamental because they are elements that can affect transaction costs. So, commitment of agents and their willingness to share knowledge is directly related to the awakening of a sense of job satisfaction and increased trust on the part of the individuals participating in the relationship.

However, the relationship between partners should be beneficial when there is a perception of fairness, especially in the early stages of the relationship, when those involved are not yet completely familiar with the working methodologies of the other partners. In this sense, the perception of fairness in the relationship improves and the willingness to do business should increase. The perception of unfairness, in the sense of obtaining undeserved advantages in negotiations, negatively affects the relationship and the willingness to cooperate between business partners and the perception of unfairness in the sense of work conflicts and the presence of injustice-conflict in corporate environments should be dealt with through a cooperative approach and technical conflict management.

Thus, this study aimed to review the international literature and understand the impact of perceptions of organizational justice on relations between agents and the governance of organizations. As such, this study is not intended to defend points of view, but rather to raise the characteristics of the debate and the insights that the issue can generate in the relationship between agents. The paper is structured as follows: after this introduction, section 2 presents the theoretical basis of the proposed topic. Section 3 presents the methodological aspects of the study. Section 4 presents the results of the

bibliometric and content analysis. Finally, the final considerations, together with some indications of trends in the discussion of the subject.

FORMAL GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES

Corporate governance mechanisms are considered vehicles used to reduce agency costs and tools capable of minimizing the destruction of market value caused by conflicts of interest between the company's participants (BOHREN; ODEGARRD, 2004). According to Colin (2007), more attention needs to be paid to the corporate governance of family businesses, state-controlled companies, and cooperatives, because in these organizations, according to the author, the owners or principal members have more power and exert greater influence on the institution.

In their study, Unterhitzenberger and Möller (2021) listed the pillars of governance: fairness, responsibility, transparency, and accountability. Musawir *et al.*, (2020) point out that the issue of equity has been neglected in governance studies, as researchers generally focus on process and policy approaches. This is confirmed by research such as that by Shleifer and Vishny (1997), who define corporate governance mechanisms as legal or economic institutions that can be altered by political processes. In this sense, Miles *et al.*, (1978) state that organizations often evaluate, adjust, and modify their mechanisms in order to achieve their purposes, thus reorganizing their roles, structures, and management processes.

According to Siqueira and Bialoskorski Neto (2014), most organizations see the dynamic process of adjusting to changes and uncertainties in the environment as a very complex process, which encompasses countless decisions and behaviors at various organizational levels. The authors claim that the complexity of adjusting processes tends to be shaped to the extent that patterns in organizational behavior are defined. And even the emotional behavior of employees has the potential to alter the patterns of organizational governance (DENG; JIA, 2022).

It is worth noting that the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2004) defines that legislation, self-regulation, or regulation of corporate governance varies from country to country, which helps to maintain reliability and the functioning of the market economy. However, Wymeersch (2005) states that the adoption of the practices set out in these codes is voluntary. Thus, their application is at the discretion of corporate bodies such as the board and management.

RELATIONAL GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES

The set of norms and rules that govern collective relationships between individuals is called relational governance (GRANDORI, 2006; BENÍTEZ-AVILA *et al.*, 2018). The social construction of these relationships tends to define the roles of individuals, production methods, and align reinforcements towards a common goal, while reducing conflicts in this network of relationships (WHITEOAK, 2014; WESTABY *et al.*, 2016).

In his study, Adamovic (2020) surveyed the impact of relationships among individuals in organizations and found that the performance of agents is usually more linked to relationships and processes among themselves than to the operational tasks of the organization. Unterhitzberger and Möller (2021) emphasize that the relational governance of a project should be viewed through the dimensions of justice in the organizational environment.

According to Poppo and Zenger (2002), relationally governed exchanges are guided by the fulfillment of obligations, expectations, promises, and social processes, which are supported by flexible and supportive norms and the exchange of information. In this way, such flexibility speeds up adaptation to unpredictable events, where problem-solving occurs in bilateral and mutual actions. Christoph (2019) reinforces the impact of relational characteristics among agents in organizations, stating that the individual behavior of agents is influenced by intrinsic motivators, such as justice, emotions, and feelings, as well as expectations, aspirations, fear, and hope. In this sense, approaches based on laws, regulations, and compliance tend to be less effective in the case of unethical behavior in the governance of organizations.

Relational governance is a construct that arises from the development of mechanisms by the organization's own individuals (BENÍTEZ-AVILA *et al.*, 2018). The same authors point out that this type of governance generally arises with the intention of controlling and encouraging collective action, generating rules, roles, practices, and functions that structure the dynamics of the organization.

Sharing information is one of the essential factors in relational governance processes, as the trust in sharing private information, such as business goals, plans, and strategies, is what generates commitment, mutuality, and cooperation among the company's stakeholders (POPPO; ZENGER, 2002). According to Uzzi (1997), it is through these social processes and norms that relational governance can help mitigate business risks. From an economic point of view, the expectation of future exchanges stimulates cooperation in the present. From a social point of view, the ties created in past negotiations converge for present and future negotiations.

In terms of research, Byrne (2015) points out that studies generally assess the economic performance of organizations, but rarely focus on the relational solutions present in institutions. The author also states that theories are generally based only on financial factors and strategic motivations to justify weaknesses in the governance structure, ignoring possible impacts generated by relational factors in corporations. This statement corroborates Larson's (1992) understanding that the presence of relational governance can mitigate the costs of time and resource allocation in companies.

ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

The theory of organizational justice was presented by Greenberg (1987) with the intention of measuring employees' perceptions of justice in organizations. Thus, the aim of the organizational justice construct is to survey the perception of how an organization's employees have been treated, whether they have been treated fairly in the workplace, and how these perceptions influence their professional performance in this environment (MOORMAN, 1991). Based on this, in a recent study, Mikami *et al.*, (2022) cite the development of a theory of equity, which is based on organizational justice, which is characterized by the maintenance of trust, restricting the opportunistic behavior of individuals.

The conclusions reached by Mikami *et al.* (2022) corroborate the findings previously made by Colquitt (2001). Accordingly, Colquitt identified that certain elements, such as organizational citizenship behavior, organizational commitment, work engagement, task performance, leadership exchange, perceived organizational support, and job satisfaction, contributed to a positive perception of fairness on the part of employees. Similarly, the presence of negative factors such as work fatigue, turnover intentions, and counterproductive behavior at work were associated with an unfavorable perception of fairness among employees.

Distributive Justice

Adams (1965) was one of the forerunners in the study of distributive justice, as he presented a framework of social exchange theory to validate the perception of justice. Adams' theory of fairness evaluates the return for one's contribution in the form of personal 'inputs' such as education, intelligence, and experience by their results (generating satisfaction, reward) compared to other collaborators. The author clarifies that the perception of the input-output relationship is completely subjective for each individual, and that distributive justice refers to the case in which employees perceive that there is equity in the relationship between their contributions and the rewards received. Currently, authors such

as Mikami *et al.* (2022), and Deng and Jia (2022), have identified the benefits of the perception of distributive justice, in the sense that transparency reinforces the importance of the equitable distribution of gains, keeping processes and decisions open and visible to all, generating a strong ethic of justice in the organization.

According to Miles (2019), distributive justice is concerned with how resources are distributed. The presence of distributive justice is perceived in corporate environments where equality and equity predominate (THIBAUT; WALKER, 1975; LEVENTHAL, 1980). The authors also point out that more recent studies have emphasized justice as a decision-making process, with a focus on expected results.

Procedural Justice

Thibaut and Walker (1975) believe that procedural justice is related to the decision-making process and how this influences the results obtained, i.e., whether the processes are perceived as fair. To be fair, they need to be ethical, accurate, representative, correct, lack bias, and consistent (LEVENTHAL, 1980). In his 2020 work, Adamovic establishes a connection between procedural justice and other facets of the concept of justice. He argues that perceptions of all these facets are often more intertwined with the relationships and procedures among agents than with the operational tasks of the organization. The author also identifies certain direct indicators for assessing the perception of procedural justice, such as the forms of treatment among team members. These indicators include precision, absence of prejudice, coherence, tone of voice, correctness, ethics, and representativeness.

Sweeney and Mcfarlin (1997) used methods to measure procedural justice by asking whether the organization's employees felt 'like losses' when changes occurred in the institution and whether the disciplinary actions taken seemed fair to them. According to the authors, these measures serve to assess procedural justice, as they are directly linked to the exploration of justice in results. In addition, Deng and Jia (2022) suggest the implementation of systems aimed at communication between superiors and subordinates as a measure to improve the perception of procedural justice.

Interactional Justice

Interactional Justice is defined as the interpersonal treatment people receive regarding the procedures they carry out (BIES; MOAG, 1986). The authors believe that the perception of interactional justice is directly related to sensitive and respectful treatment, as well as thorough guidance on the reasons for each decision by the decision-maker towards their collaborators. In a recent study, the

authors Deng and Jia (2022) even highlighted negative behavior, which they called organizational revenge, or injustice, imposed by employees on the organization in response to perceived procedural injustice, which damaged processes and altered the organization's performance.

Some researchers consider interactional justice to be a third type of justice (SKARLICK; FOLGER, 1997; BIES; SHAPIRO, 1987). However, Greenberg (1993) suggested that aspects such as respect and sensitivity are interpersonal facets of justice because they cause reactions capable of altering the results of decisions made (so even with an unfavorable outcome, sensitivity allows the employee to feel better). This perception corroborates Deng and Jia's (2022) survey, which suggests that emotions are a central mechanism, and through this, interactional justice is translated into employee performance.

In this sense, Barling and Philips (1993) identified that in an environment where interactional injustice occurs, individuals can have their results affected by withdrawal behavior. The study by Tata and Boveas-Sperry (1996) showed that women were more susceptible to the perception of interactional justice related to salary increases than men. Cropanzano and Prehar (1999), and Deng and Jia (2022) identified the influence of interactional justice on three agent variables (leader-employee exchange interactions, leader satisfaction, and leader performance evaluations).

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

In order to fulfill the proposed objective, this paper aims to quantitatively and qualitatively evaluate scientific production on the proposed theme, through a systematic review, together with a bibliometric and content analysis. In this way, it aims to identify the direction of science on the subject, as well as directing possible new research.

Steps were defined according to the PRISMA method. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow chart is a visual representation that permits the selection process of papers in a systematic review to be identified. It offers information on the total number of papers found during the initial search, as well as the number of papers that were selected or excluded throughout the systematic review process. PRISMA assists in the transparency and documentation of the selection process of the studies included in the systematic review (MOHER *et al.*, 2010).

Since publication is seen as the basis for disseminating scientific production, the more widespread it is, the better stimulates intellectual development and drives the generation of knowledge. Spinak (1998) defines bibliometrics as measuring the knowledge produced through statistical models

and quantitative methods, in such a way as to highlight the most significant aspects of the scientific community's approach to the subject under study.

In the same vein, Movahedipour *et al.*, (2016), Strucker and Hoffmann (2017), and Littell *et al.*, (2008) state that the systematic review methodology allows the literature about the study to be found and synthesized since it is based on transparent, organized, and replicable procedures. The methodology adopted in this study follows predetermined stages of organization by a research protocol, evaluates the selected articles, and summarizes their results.

The databases considered in this study were Web of Science and Scopus, due to their relevance and significance in the academic community, as well as their broad multidisciplinary content and functional tools for bibliometric analysis.

Searching scientific publication databases.

The search was based on the key words 'governance,' 'cooperatives,' and 'justice' on the Scopus and Web of Science platforms, resulting in 428 and 74 papers respectively. The research scope was delimited by applying filters: by language (English), and by year of publication (from 2019 to May 2023). It should be noted that the analysis carried out for the year 2023 was limited to papers produced up to the month of May.

To illustrate the process of organizing the filter of final papers to be analyzed, Flowchart (Figure 1) was drawn up to show the scope of the research up to this stage.

The Flowchart shows the results for each filter applied and, at the end, how many papers remained after applying all the filters. After this stage, the files were exported from the search platforms in Bibtex format and were attached to the Start software (State of the art through systematic review), which is a tool created by the Software Engineering Research Laboratory (LaPES) of the Computing Department at the Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar).

The analysis was carried out considering the items of each exported paper, in this case, the abstract, key words, and title of the remaining 123 papers. The Start tool excluded 1 paper that was duplicated in the search databases.

After this stage, 4 inclusion criteria and 2 exclusion criteria were adopted in order to fulfill the proposal of the systematic review. The inclusion criteria for the papers were 'addressing organizational justice practices in cooperatives;' 'addressing organizational justice practices in corporations;' 'addressing governance practices in corporations;' and 'addressing governance practices in cooperatives'.

And, as exclusion criteria, those papers that 'did not investigate the aspect of organizational justice in the object of study' and those that 'did not investigate the aspect of governance in the object of study.'

Figure 1- Selection process with filters in the Web of Science and Scopus databases

Source: Self elaboration.

The portfolio reached after the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the Start software too can be seen in flowchart (Figure 1). The selection is made based on the title, abstract, and key words, which are captured from the files by the program, with the intention of identifying and classifying works that are and are not compatible with the subject of the study.

Some details about the authorship of the papers, the year of publication, the title, the journal, the quartile to which the publication belongs, and the impact factor (JCI) was analyzed. JCI with the highest impact, with the Journal of Applied Psychology standing out (9.9). However, this journal does not stand out in terms of frequency of publications on the subject, since its overall contribution was only 4% during the period analyzed. Despite being mostly dedicated to psychology studies, it is clear that the

journal's impact is not strictly linked to its field or category. This is remarkable, given that research into the dynamics of organizations and companies is usually included in the category of business studies and management science, in which the Journal of World Business plays a significant role, with an impact factor of 8.9.

The quantitative analysis of the study relied on extra support tools to help visualize the results found, using the Ucinet software, the Excel spreadsheet, and the Mapchart.net and Wordart.com websites. The visual results and analysis of the results are presented in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative overview of the papers reviewed.

The behavior of scientific production, based on the selected papers, can be seen in Graphic 1. It can be observed that the highest concentration of papers is in 2020. It should be noted that in 2023, publications were limited to the month of May. This means that around 57% of the work is concentrated in the first two years of the sample.

Graphic 1 - Evolution in the volume of works within the study theme between 2019 up to 2023

Source: Self elaboration.

Some publication channels have shown themselves to be more dedicated to the subject, among them the Journal of Business Ethics and the Sustainability Journal. The other journals that have published on the subject can be seen in Graphic 2.

Graphic 2 - Participation of publications in their respective journals

Source: Self elaboration.

In the distribution of publications worldwide, 12 countries were identified, taking into account, as a criterion, the host country of the journal that published the study. In this sense, the countries that showed the greatest propensity to publish on the subject were Switzerland (21%), China (18%), and the United Kingdom and the United States, both with 14% of publications in the period studied, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Geographical distribution of publications

Source: Self elaboration.

The pattern of publications on a global level highlights the participation of developed countries in North America and Europe in the study of the subject, such as the United States, the United Kingdom,

and Denmark, for example, as well as emerging economic powers such as China and India. However, the absences also stand out, since Central America, South America, and Africa did not participate in the sample under analysis.

Regarding the studies, Figure 3 seeks to identify a network of authorship and co-authorship. In a visual representation of the networks, drawn up using the Ucinet software, it can be observed that the red balls represent the authors (28), and the blue squares represent the co-authors (66). Solo authorship was also observed, with 4 authors not seeking partnerships for their work. Some co-authors stood out because they were present in the networks of more than one author, such as co-author Hui Zahng, who published in partnership with authors Xin Su, Guannan Xi, and Shubing Guo. Co-author Alanoglu M. published with two different authors. However, apart from these exceptions, the predominant pattern is one of few connections among the studies found, due to the low number of authors and co-authors who participated in more than one paper in the period studied.

Figure 3 - Authorship and co-authorship network

Source: Self elaboration.

Figure 4 summarizes the main key words found in the studies that made up this survey. With the help of the Wordart.com website, the key words with the highest occurrence in the papers evaluated can be observed, with emphasis on the words: justice, governance, job, organizational, managing, role, effect, and social. Based on the word cloud found, it is possible to see that studies related to governance and justice tend to address their role in the working relationships of organizations.

specific organizations. The authors point to the equity-trust model as an alternative for integration, with a focus on governance, collaboration, and management, in cases of post-merger organizations.

In their study of an educational institution, Cheng *et al.* (2019) concluded that shared decision-making can structure participatory governance in schools. This model of behavior can be addressed by school leaders through tools for applying self-assessment mechanisms to students. In addition to making accountability to society clearer, in the long term, this practice tends to generate greater development in students since contact with this model of participatory governance can develop in them a sense of responsibility, both as academics and as future citizens. The study by Alanoglu and Demirtas (2020) concluded that, in educational institutions, the participatory management style of principals has a high positive predictive power on teachers' perceptions of organizational justice. While the authoritarian and indifferent management style of principals has a negative perception of the same issue on the part of teachers. Gravett and Stella (2020), and Silvernail *et al.* (2021) point to similar results in their study, which show that improvements in the performance of educational institutions are directly linked to the perception of justice in the workplace.

Liu and Yang (2021) addressed in their research the moderating effects of coopetition on the relationship between inter-firm justice and technology transfer with the aim of exploring the complex role that coopetition plays in promoting justice, informal governance mechanisms, and technology sharing.

Miles' research (2019) applied an evaluation methodology to examine students at an institution. What the author found is that the nature of the challenge influences participants' performance in terms of commitment to objectives, distributive justice, and procedural justice.

Zhang and Xi (2023), and Song *et al.* (2021) reached similar conclusions when assessing contractual influences on inter-organizational justice relationships. The authors concluded that contractual flexibility could reduce the trend towards opportunistic behavior on the part of construction service contractors and that good quality communication with contractors can help in understanding this contractual flexibility. The authors also pointed out that unlike previous studies, which focus on understanding distributive justice, this research found that procedural justice and interactional justice also have the potential to inhibit opportunistic behavior.

On the other hand, Alanoglu and Karabatak (2020) tested whether there were perceptions of organizational justice under cooperative or authoritarian management styles in the teaching staff of an educational institution. The results of the study showed that the level of perception of organizational justice among teachers, who worked in a cooperative management environment, was high and positive,

while those who worked in an authoritarian management environment had a low and negative perception.

The study by Deng and Jia (2022) highlighted a behavior presented by Wang *et al.* (2012); Jones (2009); Skarlicki and Folger (1999) found in previous research events related to justice, which have the potential to stimulate negative emotional reactions in the workplace and can generate a counter-reaction called 'anger-motivated retaliation' to punish their organization. This study sought to apply a tool called CSR, which can act in this sense, promoting a style of governance that appeases employees, and softening the perception of distributive injustice that had hitherto prevailed in the institution. The perception of injustice, in the sense of work conflicts, was also verified in Adamovic's research (2020). The author showed that the presence of injustice-conflict in corporate environments must be dealt with through a cooperative approach and technical conflict management.

The common perception of justice is relativized by Matta *et al.* (2020) who state that there is variability in the perception of justice in the day-to-day running of organizations (between 25% and 50% variation), and that this is critical because, from this point of view, various studies on the perception of justice may be incomplete. In the relationships between organizations in supply chains, elements of inter-organizational justice can be evidenced, however, according to Alghababsheh and Saikou (2022), studies on this subject are extremely scarce, more precisely, 98 papers published in peer-reviewed journals between 1983 and 2020. Unterhitzberger and Möller (2021) corroborate this understanding and add that the study of perceptions of justice and good governance also needs to address classic aspects of management and control of accountability in organizations. The authors also point out that through decision-making processes, the distribution of resources, and interactions, the typical challenges regarding the governance of inter-organizational relationships can be addressed and overcome.

Professional burnout is treated as a measure of injustice in organizations and can lead to insecurity and a drop in employee performance (ANGELIS *et al.*, 2021). According to the authors, only the promotion of organizational justice can mitigate such adverse effects in the workplace. On this same aspect, Christoph (2019) shows that there is a growing number of actions taken by employees in environments where there is a perception of organizational injustice and that this pattern of negative reaction in individual behavior has a negative impact on the organization's performance.

Riisgaard *et al.* (2020), and Alghababsheh *et al.* (2018), in their studies, discussed how the sustainability of inter-organizational relationships between suppliers and buyers, and internal relationships between employers and employees require the presence of a perception of justice (distributive, procedural, and interactional), in order to ensure the maintenance and longevity of these

relationships. This understanding corroborates the results presented in the study by Till and Yount (2018), who, based on the Agency Theory, stated that there is a need for alignment among the interests of the main agents in the organization, including promoting greater equity between hierarchical levels from the point of view of remuneration, increasing the perception of justice in the workplace. This aspect was called social justice by Ghafran and Yasmin (2019).

In their study on the governance and sustainability of rural development in fishing communities in China, He *et al.* (2021) addressed a vision called socio-ecological justice. Liao *et al.* (2019) confirm the importance of governance and perceptions of justice in the sustainable development of communities, especially regarding distributive and procedural justice.

Good governance practices and the perception of organizational justice are directly linked to sharing knowledge and information. In this sense, Cugueró-Escofet *et al.* (2019) stated that commitment and sharing knowledge is a natural step, but that it can only be seen after the feeling of job satisfaction, increased trust, and commitment that successively awakens in individuals.

In real estate negotiations, the uncertainties that permeate transactions, especially in the three dimensions of openness, fairness, and justice, mean that companies prefer to opt for a vertical governance pattern, rather than market transactions, in order to reduce transaction costs (DENG; ZHANG, 2020). The authors also point out that, from the point of view of the fairness of transaction rules, the method for determining prices in transactions must be objective, fair, and democratic.

After analyzing the content, groupings were defined for the selected papers. The groups refer to the similarities between the objects and/or individuals studied. The pattern found allowed the creation of 4 groupings, which are specified in Table 1.

Table 1 - Groupings of the papers analyzed

Group	Object of Study	Number of Studies
1	Educational institutions	5
2	Cooperative institutions	5
3	Private organizations	16
4	Public institutions/Sustainability	2

Source: Self elaboration.

Proposal of the research conceptual framework

The framework is a technique that seeks to visually contextualize the synthesis of the content, processes, patterns, and trends identified by the research. Ansari and Kant (2017), and Meredith (1993) referred to practice as constructs that are related to each other, and which seek to underpin the

foundations of the research, and possibly present new propositions and/or hypotheses. Figure 5 shows this grouping of constructs on governance and organizational justice addressed in this work.

Figure 5 - Conceptual Framework

Source: Self elaboration.

Some variables were identified in the study, such as commitment, trust, insecurity, opportunism, cooperation, contract flexibility, communication, information exchange, competition, and positive and negative feelings, for example.

The perceptions of the agents always govern negotiations, regardless of whether the relationship is between public institutions and communities, cooperatives and cooperative members, educational institutions and teachers, and/or students, or even in relationships between private institutions and clients and/or partners. In this sense, the framework sought to relate the occurrence of these variables with the perception of the constructs in the relationships among the agents that have an impact on their performance.

CONCLUSION

This study sought to understand the relationship between corporate governance and perceptions of organizational justice at a global level. However, it was not limited to the corporate world, i.e., profit-

making institutions but also the nature of the relationships among these cooperatives, educational institutions, and fishing communities, for example.

The common point among the scientific papers evaluated in this study is the agents' responses in relation to the perceived occurrence of the constructs and their variables. In other words, the higher the level of perception of good formal and/or relational governance practices, as well as distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice, the better the performance of the agents. Thus, it can be observed that the strengthening of ties between cooperative members and cooperatives has a positive impact on the lives of both the individual and the institution as a whole. The same can be said for relationships between educational institutions and students/teachers, relationships between private institutions and clients/partners, and between public institutions and communities.

In general, what was observed is that each study has its own particularities, and each group studied can present different results, but always maintain a certain degree of similarity in relation to the human behavior of the agents involved, which justifies the development of new studies on the subject, as already reinforced at an earlier point. Since there are different results, but there are also similarities among the results normally found, the more empirical research is done into the constructs and their relationships, the greater will be the support for full knowledge of the subject.

The scarcity of studies in less developed countries is also an important point to consider, and it is up to future research to identify the extent to which the knowledge generated on this subject can potentially impact the level of economic and social development in these regions.

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